

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS

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Abstract: Conditions of education modernization encourage the search for a new educational paradigm that requires professionals not only to be willing to solve professional problems, but also to ensure the use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) in order to work with information during future professional activities and to be socially mobile. The modern interpreter must establish and solve educational and cognitive information retrieval problems on their own, as well as design and apply information resources and ICT for not just modeling and implementing novel educational processes, but also for personal and professional growth. To address these issues, the prospective interpreter's personality must be well developed, as it will allow them to anticipate the existing demand for knowledge through their own cognitive activity at any time.

Key words: ICT, future teachers, English, social media, digital teaching tools, self education.

Philology Rwodzi et al. (2020) proposed a novel usage of social media to teach English as a second language. Garcia Santiago (2016) uses blogs and wikis to prepare interpreters. Ahmed et al. (2020) emphasize the need of improving English language abilities and incorporating social media into language instruction, noting that instructors must develop new teaching methodologies that integrate digital teaching tools. The article discusses the use of internet resources, namely social networks, in a person's self education. Bihych and Strilets (2020) discuss the benefits and drawbacks of ICT translation tools: Translation databases (Reverse context); electronic dictionaries (ABBYY Lingv., multitrans), required for improving and expanding potential interpreters' vocabulary; electronic text corpora as a source of authentic linguistic materials; machine translation systems (Google Translate); and CAT means (Trados, SmartCAT), capable of speeding up the compilation of the target text. Bernardini (2016) validates the use of ICT translation tools in courses that seek to improve thematic, technological, and informational abilities in information extraction for use as personal aids.

Where the concentration is on teaching foreign languages to interpreters (translation services, language, and multicultural Briaies, Filsenger, and Alonso (2018) emphasize the relevance of the lexicographic, terminological, and documentary requirements encountered during the investigation. Student translators, unlike professional translators, believe that using mobile devices is highly persuasive and handy. According to Lara (2019), machine translation has typically been connected with a translator's technological expertise. New training needs are validated: Sanchez Ramos (2017) proposes using virtual corporations as resources for public service training and translation. The translation programs are evaluated for their accuracy and relevance to real-world professional practice according to the Spanish context by (Muñoz-Miquel, 2018). The essence of the stages of the interpreter's information competence formation is revealed according to the suggestions of (Amelina&Tarasenko, 2018). In a study by Kuzminskyi et al. (2019), the types of information needed in the postgraduate education system of faculty were classified. Electronic information resources of Olalla-Soler (2018) have been used for solving cultural translation problems. Schaeffer et al. (2020) offered a

translation accuracy survey questionnaire: an on-line tool for researching interpreters, which formed the basis of the author's questionnaire. Olalla-Soler (2019) applied internalized knowledge about the culture of the source to solve problems of cultural translation in a quasi-experimental study of the translator's acquisition of cultural competence in different languages and cultures. Sycz-Opoń (2019) substantiated the informational behavior of translation students of Silesia University in the process of legal translation. Esfandiari et al. (2019) carried out an assessment of European Master's in Translation framework for its compatibility with the needs of a professional interpreter. The development of professional competence of future translator's in a two-way translation has been observed by modern methods (Popova, 2019). Despite the fact that a substantial number of scientific studies have contributed to the solution to this problem, it can be argued that the subject of professional training of future translators at the classical university has received insufficient attention in current educational research. The objective of this paper is to identify the characteristics of professional training for prospective translators at a classical institution. Thus, it is determined that the substantive basis of organizational and pedagogical conditions for the formation of information competency of future translators in professional training is multilevel information tasks of translators' professional activity, which create continuous methodological lines in learning concepts and forming ways to solve translation and information problems.

It has been demonstrated that prioritizing active and interactive methods of developing future translators' information competency with the help of modern teaching aids creates conditions for personal growth and experience in performing translational and informational tasks in the role of a professional translator. The planned organizational and pedagogical circumstances for forming prospective translators' information competency during professional training mirror the peculiarities of professional training at a classical institution. Further study on this subject includes the introduction of simulation technologies, computer modeling, aspects of geographical information systems and mobile, cluster technologies, comparative analysis of existing foreign and domestic technologies for training translators, the use of modern

high-tech tools, energy-efficient technologies, and telecommunications in education in order to determine the most effective ones for the development of information competency, further development of methodology aimed at the formation of information competency of students, improving the model of formation of information competency of translators.

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